

Azerbaijan University of
Architecture and Construction

Istanbul Technical University

Ministry of Emergency Situations
of the Republic of Azerbaijan

University North

**Dedicated to the 50th Anniversary
of the Azerbaijan University
of Architecture and Construction**

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
**MODERN
CIVIL ENGINEERING
PROBLEMS**

MCEP 2025

JUNE 24-25, BAKU, AZERBAIJAN

<https://mcepazuac.org>

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condition of the surrounding landscapes, reducing the transport load of the territory, reducing the shortage of land for development in the city center, etc.

In conclusion, the main factors that make rehabilitation projects for the historically established industrial areas of Absheron unprofitable in terms of additional costs are: severe deterioration of engineering and technical communications in the industrial territories of Absheron, doubts about the suitability of the structure for use after renovation and the combination of its new functions with the surrounding urban context, insufficiency of regulatory - legal documents defining the status of territories, the difficulty of obtaining approvals, as well as insufficient development of issues of economic, environmental and socio-cultural justification for the regeneration project.

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Socio-Ecological Aspects of Urban Settlement Development in the Mountainous Shirvan Region of Azerbaijan

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Abstract— *this study investigates the socio-ecological challenges and urban development opportunities within the Mountainous Shirvan region of Azerbaijan. The article adopts and interdisciplinary framework grounded in ecological urbanism, climate-resilient spatial planning and regional development theory. Employing mixed methods approach involving spatial analysis, policy review and statistical data analysis the research provides an examination of key environmental and socio-economic challenges affecting urban sustainability. A significant focus is placed on green urban interventions, decentralized planning models and data-informed zoning regulations to foster ecological sustainability and socio-economic resilience.*

The findings reveal critical mismatches between planning capacity and ecological urgency, particularly in peri-urban zones vulnerable to deforestation and seismic risk. Additionally, youth outmigration and infrastructure deficits hamper long-term resilience. However, recent pilot projects in green infrastructure and reforestation suggest that context-sensitive interventions can catalyze transformation. This proposes and integrated urban strategy for mountainous settlements combining green infrastructure, land-use reform, and community-based urban design. The outcomes aim to contribute to a roadmap for inclusive, sustainable development aligned with national and global frameworks.

Keywords— *socio-ecological development, sustainable urbanism, Mountainous Shirvan, Azerbaijan, green infrastructure,*

resilience

I. INTRODUCTION

Urban areas in mountainous regions are highly sensitive to ecological degradation, climate change and economic marginalization. The Mountainous Shirvan region of Azerbaijan – comprising Shamakhi, Ismailli, Agsu and Gobustan – is a pertinent case where environmental fragility intersects with spatial inequality and underdeveloped urban services. With Azerbaijan aiming to align national planning with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities) and SDG 13 (Climate Action), there is growing policy interest in resilient and inclusive urban development. However, implementation gaps and a lack of contextualized research remain challenges.

Urban planning in Mountainous Shirvan region is complicated by seismic activity, steep terrain, ecological degradation and declining human capital [3:9;16]. According to the State Statistical committee (2023), the region's urban population accounts for approximately 43% of the total 278 000 residents, with outmigration rates exceeding 19% over the last decade, especially among youth aged 18-35.

Urban development in the region is constrained by historical underinvestment, limited municipal capacity and fragmented land tenure systems. However, emerging policy frameworks and international cooperation have opened a window of opportunity for transformative planning. This paper aims to advance a comprehensive and empirically grounded urban development strategy based on socio-ecological priorities and sustainable spatial models tailored to mountainous regions.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This paper applies a mixed research methods:

- Spatial analysis. Land-use and vegetation cover trends were assessed using satellite imagery (2000-2023) from Copernicus and Landsat databases.
- Longitudinal population data (19980-2023), infrastructure access (water, electricity, sanitation) and economic indicators were extracted from Azerbaijan's national statistics portal and supplemented by field surveys;
- Policy review. Documents analyzed include the 2024-2028 State Program, Urban Development Law (2023) and municipal climate action plans.

III. STATUS OF THE ISSUE

Socio-ecological urbanism has emerged as a critical paradigm for sustainable development in vulnerable geographies. Ahern [1] introduced the concept of "safe-to-fall" urban systems for resilience, advocating for adaptive, multifunctional, and ecologically embedded urban design. The Mountain Research Initiative [10] underscores that mountainous urban systems require spatial policies that align biodiversity conservation with social equity. Scholars such as Todde [4] have emphasized the need for participatory governance and integrated watershed management in mountain settlements.

In post-socialist countries, urban transformation remains shaped by path-dependent institutional legacies. Gentile [6] and Golubchikov [7] highlight the inertia of centralized planning instruments. Azerbaijani urban studies [2; 8; 12] reveal that although sustainability discourse is present in national strategies, municipal adaptation mechanisms are undeveloped.

Globally, sustainable mountainous urbanization is aligned with the UN's Sendai Framework, the Paris Agreement and SDG11 [15; 14]. Yet implementation requires localized metrics. The OECD [11] suggests the remote urban centers need special planning zones, digital governance and green investment packages to overcome geographic and infrastructural isolation

Mountainous Shirvan is ecologically diverse but environmentally vulnerable. The region experiences seismic risks, soil erosion, and water scarcity [5]. With a combined population of approximately 278 000, urban settlements remain semi-rural in morphology. Data from the State Statistical Committee [13] indicate a 19% youth outmigration over the past decade and declining agricultural productivity.

IV. REGIONAL OVERVIEW: MOUNTAINOUS SHIRVAN IN TRANSITION

The Mountainous Shirvan region spans 9 840 km², with altitude ranging from 300 to 2400 meters above sea level. Urban expansion has occurred unevenly. Shamakhi has grown by 6,8% over the past 15 years, while Aghsu has shrunk by 3,1%. Most urban zones lack formally planned boundaries and rely on inherited Soviet layouts, with less than 15% of settlements possessing detailed land-use plans.

Environmental Pressure and Urban Form. Satellite imagery reveals a 12,4% reduction in forest cover between 2000 and 2003, largely due to peri-urban expansion and illegal logging. Urban layouts remain car-centric and fragmented, with limited green space accessibility (average 3.2 m² per capita vs WHO minimum of 9 m²). Annual per capita renewable water availability is below 900 m³ [5]. Shamakhi city lies in zone of 9 of the Modified Mercalli Scale.

V. DISCUSSIONS

Urban settlements are largely low-density and mono-functional. Agricultural land encroachment and informal housing dominate peri-urban zones. Only 3% of surveyed areas possess protected ecological zones within urban boundaries.

24% of population is youth (15-35). Average commute time to services 41 minutes. Access to piped water is 62%, to waste water treatment – 38%.

Green Urbanism Initiatives. Pilot projects include Passive solar housing in Ismayilli (UNDP-funded), agro-ecological parks in Aghsu, co-managed by local cooperatives and community forestry in Shamakha (1300 ha reforested). While promising, these projects lack scale and integration into statutory plans.

According to analysis author offers urban planning recommendations for urban settlement development in Mountainous Shirvan region:

1. Eco-zoning and land-use reform. Redefine urban growth boundaries using ecosystem-based planning;
2. Green urban corridors and terraced settlements. Use bio-technical engineering to stabilize slopes. Develop ecological corridors linking urban centers with protected forest zones;
3. Water Sensitive Urban design. Incorporate decentralized stormwater management systems, rain gardens and greywater reuse in new development;
4. Digital Urban governance. Establish open-access planning platforms using smart GIS dashboards for land use monitoring;
5. Community-based urbanism. Institutionalize participatory planning boards. Expand environmental education in secondary schools and vocational programs.

VI. CONCLUSION

Urban settlements in Mountainous Shirvan must pivot from reactive, project-based development to proactive, integrated territorial planning. This transformation

necessitates a socio-ecological planning model supported by data, regional cooperation and meaningful community inclusion.

A shift toward integrated green infrastructure and nature-based development solutions can restore degraded ecosystems while enhancing liveability and economic opportunity. Empowering local governments through fiscal reform, education and digital tools is also essential. By embedding resilience and sustainability into spatial policy, the Mountainous Shirvan region can serve as a replicable model for other mountainous urban systems confronting the dual crises of ecological degradation and social disinvestment.

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A Paradigm Shift: Exploring the Role of Large Language Models in Architecture Studio Pedagogy

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Abstract—The emergence of large language models (LLMs) marks a profound epistemological and pedagogical shift in architecture education. The very definition of what constitutes creativity and whether the input of the machine can be considered such are fundamental, interconnected, and emerging questions. Nevertheless, our lived experience in an architecture studio reveals that almost all students utilise LLMs in various capacities. Therefore, architectural pedagogy must confront this paradigm shift by addressing it constructively. Architecture pedagogy is renowned for its flexibility and resilience in adopting new technologies; accordingly, the rapid pace of AI integration makes it urgent to address the theoretical foundation of the issue. From a theoretical standpoint, the discourse examines the role of LLMs as co-agents in the design generation process, raising fundamental questions about authorship, originality, and the mediation of knowledge. This paper conducts a systematic literature and bibliometric review to critically examine the transformative nature and ontological implications of integrating Large Language Models (LLMs) into architecture studio

pedagogy. Through mapping the emerging discourses, we expose both the promises and paradoxes of LLMs in fostering dialogue, performative optimisation, and new modalities of collaborative learning. However, this paradigm shift must be considered together with ethical ambiguity and the potential erosion of critical and creative autonomy. The paper concludes by outlining research gaps and a critical agenda for future studies, emphasising the need for a nuanced, reflexive, and ethically grounded approach to AI integration in architectural education.

Keywords—large language models, architecture studio pedagogy, human-computer interaction, creative agency.

I. INTRODUCTION

The integration of generative artificial intelligence (AI) and large language models (LLMs) into architectural education is affecting traditional pedagogies of architecture. The design studio education has found a new digital member